

SEMI-ACTIVE PIEZOELECTRIC TUNED MASS DAMPER FOR MITIGATION OF AERODYNAMIC VIBRATIONS IN AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES

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Abstract. The analytical framework of a semi active tuned mass damper (SATMD) is developed for the reduction of low-frequency aerodynamic vibrations in aeronautics structures. The SATMD entails a shunted piezoelectric connected in series to an RL electric circuit. Initially, the theoretical model of the SATMD is presented, including the equivalent electrical RL circuit, applied on a simplified system consisting of two structural modes. Subsequently, the SAMTD concept is evaluated experimentally on a scaled-down simplified aircraft prototype constructed for this purpose. Finally, the simulated model is correlated with experimental measurements. In summary, both experimental and numerical results, illustrate that by choosing an appropriate auxiliary mass for the SATMD a specific mode can be targeted and can be substantially damped using a properly tuned shunt resistor. Subsequently the inductance can retune the system to another mode of interest. The obtained results indicate capabilities to reduce the structural acceleration of the main structure up to 20dB.

1 INTRODUCTION

Excessive vibrations may lead to material fatigue and structural failure. In addition, regarding their repercussions on aeronautic structures may cause discomfort both to the passengers and the pilots. A well-established method of passive vibration absorption is the inclusion of a device to reduce vibration levels of the main structure [1],[2]. Such devices are called dynamic vibrations absorbers (DVA) or tuned mass dampers (TMD). The classic TMD consists of a mass-spring-damper system tuned on a specific frequency of interest in the manner that the kinetic energy of the main mass is transferred to the auxiliary mass of the TMD and subsequently dissipated through the dashpot. However, a passive TMD is hindered by a phenomenon called 'detuning' caused by deterioration of the mechanical properties of the structure for example mass change due to fuel consumption. In such cases a passive TMD ceases to be effective until it is retuned. Another method to enhance the damping of the structure [3] has been proposed by Hagood and Von Flotow in 1991 [4], where a piezoelectric patch is attached on a beam connected with a resistive and inductive shunts [5]-[7]. Part of the

mechanical energy due to the piezoelectric effect is transformed to electric energy which causes charge to flow through the electric circuit and is dissipated by the resistor. This circuit is equivalent to adding a spring-mass-damper, with the inductor adding virtual mass, the resistor being the damper and the material capacitance being the spring. Optimal tuning of the RL values can be obtained using the Den Hartog method [9].

Taking into consideration the aforementioned crucial drawback of a passive TMD, a semi active tuned mass damper [10],[11] (consisted of an auxiliary mass and a piezoelectric stack connected in series with an RL electric circuit) is proposed. The SATMD offers tuning flexibility while retaining the robustness of the passive system. That is to say, the baseline vibration reduction of the SATMD at a single frequency is provided by the tuned auxiliary mass, while the introduction of electromechanical inertia by the inductor provides additional vibration reduction by dissipation of the electric energy through a resistor.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Initially, in Section 2 the equations of motion for the baseline structure modeled by two structural modes whose modal characteristics are predicted by modal analysis of a detailed Abaqus FEA model. Then the theoretical framework of the coupled electromechanical system (the structure with the SATMD attached and the RL network) is presented. Subsequently on Section 3 the SAMTD concept is evaluated on a scaled-down simplified aircraft prototype manufactured for this purpose. Furthermore, the experimental validation with the numerical predictions are presented in Section 4. Finally, in Section 5 are entailed the concluding remarks of the proposed work along with suggestions for future work.

2 FORMULATION

2.1 Baseline structure model

Considering the fact that the simplified structure is modelled by two structural modes, as shown in Figure 1, the modal displacements can be derived by the following second order differential equation,

$$\begin{aligned} [\Phi]^T \cdot [m] \cdot [\Phi] \cdot \ddot{\underline{q}}(t) + [\Phi]^T \cdot [c] \cdot [\Phi] \cdot \dot{\underline{q}}(t) + [\Phi]^T \cdot [k] \cdot [\Phi] \cdot \underline{q}(t) &= \underline{\Phi}^T \cdot \underline{F}(t) \\ [M] \cdot \ddot{\underline{q}}(t) + [C] \cdot \dot{\underline{q}}(t) + [K] \cdot \underline{q}(t) &= \underline{P}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\underline{q}(t) = \{q_1(t), q_2(t)\}^T$ is the vector of modal displacements, $[\Phi]$ is the 2×2 modal matrix of the eigenvectors, $[m]$, $[c]$ and $[k]$ are the mass, damping and stiffness matrices respectively, while $\underline{F}(t)$ is the applied force., $[M]$, $[C]$ and $[K]$ are the 2×2 modal mass, modal damping and modal stiffness matrices respectively and $\underline{P}(t)$ is the modal force vector. Finally, the transformation back to physical coordinates can be performed as follows

$$\underline{x}(t) = [\Phi] \cdot \underline{q}(t) \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Baseline Structure Modal Representation

The baseline model parameters $[M], [\omega^n], [\zeta]$ are shown in Table 1, which were extracted from a detailed Abaqus FEA model of the Lab scale prototype presented in Section 3.

Table 1: Modal Data

	$i = 1$	$i = 2$	
M^i	4.09	4.38	[kg]
ω_i^n	48.8	65.3	[Hz]
ζ^i	0.1	0.1	[%]

2.2 Structure with SATMD attached model

Assuming that the auxiliary mass and the piezostack stiffness are too small to change the mode shapes of the baseline structure, the new system (as shown on Figure 2) equations can be formulated.

Figure 2: Structure with SATMD attached Representation

Therefore, one more degree of freedom is added as the displacement of the auxiliary mass, as well as one more degree of freedom for the electrical charge that flows from the external network. Hence, the electromechanical system can be described by the following second order differential equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \begin{bmatrix} M & 0 & -e \cdot L \cdot \varphi_n^T \\ 0 & m_a & e \cdot L \\ 0 & 0 & L \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \ddot{q} \\ \ddot{x}_a \\ \ddot{Q}_2 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} C + c_a \cdot \varphi_n^T \cdot \varphi_n & c_a \cdot \varphi_n^T & -e \cdot R \cdot \varphi_n^T \\ c_a \cdot \varphi_n & c_a & e \cdot R \\ 0 & 0 & R \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{q} \\ \dot{x}_a \\ \dot{Q}_2 \end{Bmatrix} + \\
 & + \begin{bmatrix} K + k_a \cdot \varphi_n^T \cdot \varphi_n & k_a \cdot \varphi_n^T & 0 \\ k_a \cdot \varphi_n & k_a & 0 \\ e/C_p \cdot \varphi_n & -e/C_p & 1/C_p \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} q \\ x_a \\ Q_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} P \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where x_a is the physical displacement of the auxiliary mass, m_a, c_a and k_a is the auxiliary mass, actuator damping and stiffness respectively, e is the piezoelectric coefficient and C_p is the stack capacitance.

Table 2: SATMD Properties

k_a	87	[kN / m]
m_a	574	[g]
ζ_a	1.4	[%]
e	0.73	[N / V]
C_p	40	[μF]

The SATMD properties shown in Table 2 were experimentally identified by a series of tests on the device solely.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Experimental Setup

The manufactured scaled-down simplified aircraft weights approximately 112 kg and consists of the following components:

- a 3m steel tubular beam representing the fuselage of the aircraft
- two aluminum plate-strips for the wings and the horizontal tail and
- Three plastic connectors made of ACETAL, for the mounting of the wings, the horizontal tail and the SATMD of the horizontal tube. All the aforementioned components are illustrated in Figure 3.

a)

b)

Figure 3: Design of Lab scale Aircraft Prototype; a) FEM model; b) Actual prototype

3.2 Experimental procedure

In order to simulate realistic testing flight conditions, the model was suspended with elastic belts from the modal points of the first bending modal frequency ($L/4$ and $3L/4$). The SATMD anti-vibration setup is placed on the Lab Prototype tip with the mechanism facing downwards. An electromechanical shaker was mounted at the middle of the rear horizontal tail, under the fuselage to excite the structure. The shaker was equipped with a load cell to measure the applied force on the prototype. A pair of accelerometers were used to measure the response located. One on the tip on the top of the tubular beam, while the second was located at the tip and the middle of the horizontal aluminium beam simulating the aircraft wing. The applied actuation

signal was a swept sine within the range of 1 to 200 Hz. The generated acceleration at the measuring locations as well as the applied force were collected via a National Instruments DAQ board, digitized and the corresponding frequency response functions were prepared.

This procedure was repeated with and without the SATMD attached to compare the system performance. Figure 4 presents the critical modal frequencies for the performed experimental analysis of the baseline, which are the 1st bending wing mode at 36Hz, the 1st bending modal frequency across the length of the fuselage at 48Hz and the 2nd bending modal frequency across the length of the fuselage at 65Hz.

Figure 4: Baseline Prototype Acceleration Response

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Mass Tuning at the 1st Bending Frequency (48 Hz)

Initially, an auxiliary mass of 1027 g was used to tune the SATMD at the first bending frequency of the structure (48Hz), in order to study its performance for various resistance levels connected to the SATMD terminals. Initially, the response of the structure was measured without the presence of the SATMD as baseline, then the resistance was gradually increased and finally the case of the open circuit was examined (passive operation). Figure 5 shows the experimental results while in Figure 6 the formulated model is presented which appears to be in good agreement with the experimental measurements. In both cases the optimal resistance was found to be at 50Ω . Increasing the resistance beyond that value the response of the structure starts to increase again.

Figure 5: Measured Response for Variable Resistance levels Tuned at 48Hz

Figure 6: Simulated Response for Variable Resistance levels Tuned at 48Hz

Figure 7, presents a more complete picture of the reduction in dB of the acceleration compared to the baseline system achieved by various resistance levels in the neighbour of 40 to 50 Hz.

Both the experiment and the simulation present the same trends with the optimal value being at 50Ω . However the analytical model predicts a reduction of $28dB$ in comparison to the measured reduction of $26dB$ from the baseline at the experiment. This difference is negligible considering that in both cases the remaining oscillation is

Figure 7: Effect of Resistance at the neighbour of 48 Hz

4.2 Mass Tuning at the 2nd Bending Frequency (65 Hz)

For the case of the 2nd bending mode, the SATMD was tuned by using a mass 574 g. Consequently, a shunt resistor was connected on the SATMD terminals while multiple resistance levels were examined up to the case of an open circuit (passive operation). A maximum reduction of 23 dB was achieved at the optimum resistance level of 91Ω as shown on Figure 8. Simultaneously, a 9 dB reduction on the first mode was observed. In Figure 9, the predictions of the analytical model are presented, whose results are in line with the experimental measurements.

Figure 8: Measured Response for Variable Resistance levels Tuned at 65Hz

Figure 9: Simulated Response for Variable Resistance levels Tuned at 65Hz

Figure 10 presents the reduction of acceleration in dB compared to the baseline system in the neighbour of 60 to 75 Hz for various resistance levels.

Both the experiment and the simulation illustrate the same trends with the optimal value being at. However there is a discrepancy since the simulation predicts a reduction of 30dB in comparison to the measured reduction of 24dB from the baseline at the experiment.

Figure 10: Effect of Resistance at the neighbour of 65 Hz

4.2.1 Operation under variable inductive loads.

Furthermore, the effect of inductance to the system performance was examined, aiming to retune the SATMD from the 1st bending frequency to the 2nd. Thus, we mounted on the tip of the fuselage the SATMD with 574 gr auxiliary mass providing tuning of the mechanism at 65Hz. The performance of the lab prototype was measured with various inductance-resistance levels connected on the terminals of the SATMD. The mentioned resistance was the one measured at the terminals of the actuator when the inductor was connected. Figure 11 presents the measured FRFs at the neighbour of the tuning frequency (65Hz), while Figure 12 illustrates the FRFs of the response at the neighbour of the 1st bending modal frequency at 48Hz. Significant reduction is achieved simultaneously at both modal frequencies as the inductive load increases.

Figure 11: Measured Response for Variable Inductance levels in the neighbour of 65Hz

Figure 12: Measured Response for Variable Inductance levels in the neighbour of 48Hz

The overall performance of the anti-vibration setup with various inductive loads is illustrated in Figure 13. The achieved reduction on the 1st modal frequency as the inductance increases, while the mechanism is mechanically tuned at the 2nd modal frequency at 65Hz. The measured performance illustrates a reduction up to the level of 16dB for inductance values of 150mH

Figure 13: Effect of Inductance at the neighbour of 48 Hz

5 CONCLUSIONS

The scope of the present work was to develop an antivibration setup capable to tune at different frequencies. The proposed solution, the Semi-Active Tuned Mass Damper (SATMD) based on the support of the auxiliary TMD mass on a piezoceramic stack actuator, while a resistance and an inductor are connected parallel to the actuator. The presence of the resistance on the system adds damping via dissipation of the oscillation energy as the form of heat to the resistance terminals. Additionally, the dynamic characteristics of the inductor add virtual inertia on the oscillated mechanical system providing the flexibility to the SATMD to be tuned at various modal frequencies. Multiple tuning cases were examined and compared to the performance of the baseline system. Initially, the performance of a system while having solely adaptive resistance and concluding with the application of a R-L external network.

The manufactured lab-test prototype confirmed the analytical assumptions and the predicted dynamic characteristics were measured and validated. Two critical modal frequencies were identified, the 1st bending frequency at 48Hz and the 2nd bending at 65Hz.

Consequently, the assembled SATMD was attached on the prototype and tested under external mechanical excitation. The system was tested under various resistances, elucidating an optimal resistance of maximum performance of 91Ω with $23dB$ reduction at the tuned frequency, while at the same time the other resonance peak introduced a reduction of $9dB$.

Furthermore, by keeping the resistance constant, various values of inductance were applied. The outcome of this specific test was, that while changing the inductance the performance of the system could be tuned to a different frequency, resulting at an optimum value of $150mH$ with $16dB$ maximum reduction.

Finally, analytical simulations using the developed reduced-order mode superposition model were performed and correlated to the experimental measurements in order to validate the model. The correlations indicate that the analytical model is able to replicate very well the measured results concerning the effect of resistance. Regarding the effect of inductance discrepancies were observed, this specific issue seems to be quite complex and requires further investigation possibly due to nonlinearities of the piezoelectric stack thus requiring further investigation.

To sum up, the measured semi-active vibration reductions on the tested prototype has successfully demonstrated the feasibility of the proposed concept. The developed modelling tools produced reasonably good predictions of the measured prototype response.

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